

EARTH SCIENCES

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR CALCULATING HYDROCARBON RESERVES BASED ON ELECTRICAL LOGGING DATA

Seyidov V.M.

Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Azadlig Avenue 16/21, Az 1010, Baku, Azerbaijan; professor

Melikov K.F.

Binagadi Oil Company, Binagadi settlement, 3rd mine, Az 1053, Baku, Azerbaijan; assistant professor

Abstract

Purpose and object of research: the purpose of the study - development of a new interpretation method for determining petrophysical quantities used in calculating oil reserves based on mining geophysical data; the object of research - is oil fields that have been in development for a long time.

Methods and means of solving the problem: method - methods of interpretation of electrical logging data; tools - digitization program, interpretation formulas for calculating petrophysical quantities in Excel.

Method and methodology: method - conversion of electrical logging diagrams into digital las files using Neuralog program, calculation of petrophysical quantities according to substantiated formulas using Excel program; methodology - development of a new method.

Research results: New methods for determining the porosity coefficient have been developed for recalculation of oil saturation using electrical logging (A2M0.5N) in the well stock of long-term developed oil fields and using the well potential curve. Using this information, various maps, sections, models were constructed and suggestions were made based on the analysis.

Keywords: well logging methods, electrical logging, deposits, layers, well, porosity, oil saturation, clayness, sandness, etc.

1. Introduction

Research data play a leading role in studying the geological section of oil and gas fields by geophysical methods. Therefore, geophysical research in each oil field is divided into three stages. Structure of the field is studied by seismic; for field structure by electrical, gravimetric survey methods and well cross-section by mining geophysics methods [1]. In order to assess the state of development of the long-operating Pirallahi field in the Apsheron archipelago, research materials measured in the geophysical section of 443 wells discovered by this object were surveyed using existing processing programs and the necessary database for analysis was created.

It should be note that, like many oil and gas fields, the balance of oil reserves in the Pirallahi field has been calculated several times during operation. The last calculation was made in 2002 [2].

Taking into account technical and economic factors, the number of fully explored wells in the field is 5-10%. Oil reserves are calculated based on the results of these well surveys and laboratory analysis of a small number of rock samples.

The sequence of the newly proposed study is as follows: 1) new interpretation methods are being developed for the calculation of petrophysical quantities; 2) a list of wells on tectonic blocks is prepared; 3) converts SER (specific electric resistance) and spontaneous potential (SP) curves from analog to digital according to the Neuralog program for all wells; 4) SER, α_{SP} and new methods $\Delta\alpha_{SP}$, K_p , K_{os} , C_c , C_s , as well as h are determined by the application of the program on the basis of digital data with 1 m interval (on all wells, along the entire section); 5) including the

above-mentioned quantities on blocks, intervals exceeding K_{os} 52 % are selected and collected. In the end, along with the quantities h_o and h_{og} , the average value of the mentioned quantities is determined; 6) On the basis of the second part of 4, the average quantities required for the calculation of the reserve on the blocks is given in the form of a table on the suite, and the initial reserve is calculated; 7) the oil reserves produced by formation groups are deducted from the initial reserves and the current oil reserves are determined, and the oil recovery factor is determined by dividing; 8) field distribution maps and 3D model are constructed and analyzed;

2. Methods used and proposed

Methods used [7, 8, 9, 10, 13]:

The main parameters that characterize the filtration-capacity of the collector layers at the development site are porosity, effective thickness and hydrocarbon saturation, etc. These quantities are determined by the following known formulas:

- Determination of effective thickness

$$h_{ef} = H_{total} * (1 - C_c) \quad (1)$$

Here, H_{total} - total thickness of the layer; C_c - is the coefficient of clayness.

- Porosity is determined by both electrical logging and spontaneous potential (SP). The Archie-Hamble formula is applied in electrical logging [14, 15, 18, 28]:

$$P_r = \frac{\alpha_{SP}}{K_p^m} = \frac{\rho_{w,rock}}{\rho_{laywater}} \quad (2)$$

$$K_p = K_p^{max} - K_{lay} C_c \quad (3)$$

Here, P_r - relative specific resistance; α - is a coefficient equal to 1; K_p - collector porosity coefficient; $\rho_{w.rock}$ - special resistance of water-bearing bed; $\rho_{laywater}$ - special resistance layer water; C_c - is the coefficient of clayiness; K_p^{max} - maximum coefficient of porosity on the cross-section; m - is a coefficient, reflecting the structure of the rock ($m=2$ was accepted in the investigation).

- The coefficient clayiness is determined on the basis of $\alpha_{SP} = f(C_c)$ dependence on SP:

$$\alpha_{SP} = \frac{U_{SP}}{U_{SP,max}} \quad (4)$$

Here, U_{SP} - the value of the SP in front of studied collector layers; $U_{SP,max}$ - is the value of the SP in front of "clean" sandstone.

- The following formulas are available to determine the saturation coefficient:

$$K_{o.g} = K_{o.g}^{max} (1 - C_c) \frac{K_p^{max}}{K_p^{lay}} \quad (5)$$

Here, $K_{o.g}^{max}$ - maximum saturation coefficient on cross-section; C_c - is the coefficient of clayiness; K_p^{max} - maximum coefficient of porosity on the cross-section; K_p^{lay} - porosity coefficient of the studied layer.

For clayly-sandstone according to Pupou [21, 22, 25, 26, 27]

$$K_{water} = \frac{0.9}{K_p} \sqrt{(1/\rho_{lay} - C_c/\rho_c)\rho_{water}(1 - C_c)} ;$$

$$K_{o.g} = 1 - \frac{0.9}{K_p} \sqrt{(1/\rho_{lay} - C_c/\rho_c)\rho_{water}(1 - C_c)} \quad (6)$$

For clean-sandstone according to De Utta

$$K_{water} = \frac{0.9}{K_p} \sqrt{(1/\rho_{lay} - C_c/\rho_c)C_c} ;$$

Figure 1. The transition curve from the assumed spesific resistance value to the true resistance value

The mentioned methodology was applied between SER and true resistance value of formation PKS and

$$K_{o.g} = 1 - \frac{0.9}{K_p} \sqrt{(1/\rho_{lay} - C_c/\rho_c)C_c} \quad (7)$$

According to Simandoux

$$K_{water} = \left[C_c/\rho_c + \sqrt{(C_c/\rho_c)^2 + 5(K_p^2)} \right] \frac{0.4\rho_{water}}{K_p^2} ;$$

$$K_{o.g} = 1 - \left[C_c/\rho_c + \sqrt{(C_c/\rho_c)^2 + 5(K_p^2)} \right] \frac{0.4\rho_{water}}{K_p^2} \quad (8)$$

According to Dolly

$$K_{water} = \frac{1}{K_p} \left[(0.81\rho_{water}/\rho_c)^{1/n} - C_c(\rho_{water}/(0.4\rho_c))^{1/n} \right]$$

$$K_{o.g} = 1 - \frac{1}{K_p} \left[(0.81\rho_{water}/\rho_c)^{1/n} - C_c(\rho_{water}/(0.4\rho_c))^{1/n} \right] \text{ets.} \quad (9)$$

Here, K_p - porosity coefficient of collector; C_c - is the coefficient of clayiness; ρ_{lay} - special resistance of layer; ρ_{water} - special resistance of layer water; ρ_c - special resistance of clay layer; K_{water} - coefficient of water saturation; $K_{o.g}$ - coefficient of oil-gas saturation.

3. Suggested methods [3, 4, 5, 6, 11, 12, 16, 17, 19, 20, 23, 24].

New methods for determining the mentioned quantities have been developed in the following sequence:

a) Determination of true resistance. For this purpose, using well survey data measured with a complete geophysical complex, the value of the true resistance (ρ_{lay}) determined at the cross-section is based on a comparison of the assumed specific resistance (ρ_{SER}) with the standard zonde (N0.5M2A) transition to the true value (ρ_{lay}) using the dependence curve (fig.1), the following formula is determined:

$$\rho_{lay} = 0,995\rho_{SER}^{0,843} \quad (R^2=0,998) \quad (10)$$

Here, ρ_{SER} - assumed specific electric resistance.

KS and, as can be seen, a linear relationship was obtained (fig. 2).

Figure 2. $\rho_{SER} = f(\rho_h)$ dependence for formation PKS and KS

b) Determination of porosity coefficient. Petrophysical and geophysical data collected on the field are analyzed in order to assess the collector parameters in the rocks at the cross-section of wells drilled at the development object. For this purpose, values of the determination porosity coefficient based on the analysis of rock samples taken during excavation from the cross-section of the object, by compiling the dependence

curve α_{SP} determined by electric logging from porosity at the same intervals (fig. 3) and the following formula was obtained.

$$K_p = 0,258\alpha_{SP}^{0,5} \quad (R^2=0,975) \quad (11)$$

α_{SP} - relative spontaneous potential.

Figure 3. Dependence curve α_{SP} from value of rock samples porosity

c) Determination of oil saturation coefficient. Complete and limited complex researches are carried out at the cross-section of wells that open the object during drilling in the field, by the methods of mining geophysics. Taking into account technical and economic factors, the number of wells measured in the field with full geophysical complex is 5-10 %. Only after the investigation of these wells, an opinion characterizing the qualitative or quantitative parameters of the filtration-capacity characteristics of the section collectors is given, and these opinions are used as basic information in the calculation of the balance oil and gas reserves of the field. The time difference between the drilling period of these wells, the complex lithological composition of the cross-section, change in area along the vertical and horizontal directions, shielding with transverse and longitudinal disturbances, tectonic block

fraction in the calculation of reserves and the small number of wells measured in a complete geophysical complex in the analysis of development, adversely affects the results of inventory calculation and analysis, and most fields need to be reassessed. For this purpose, when assessing the development status of the object analyzed by the field research method, using research data on complete and limited geophysical complexes in wells, quantitative parameters of collectors are determined at the cross-section. For this purpose, using well survey data measured in a complete geophysical complex, the following formula was obtained for oil and gas saturation (fig. 4):

$$K_{o.g} = 0,454\rho_{lay}^{0,157} \quad (R^2=0,998) \quad (12)$$

ρ_{lay} - true value of the special resistance of layer;

Figure 4. Dependence curve on the true resistance of the oil-bearing formation

d) Calculation of clayness coefficient. The following formula (anisotropic method) was used for this purpose:

$$C_g = \frac{(\rho_{cal}^{max} - \rho_{cal})\rho_c}{(\rho_{cal}^{max} - \rho_c)\rho_{cal}} * 100\% \quad (13)$$

Here, ρ_{cal} - is the true specific resistance obtained for the layers by calculation; ρ_c - special resistance of clay layer (this value is taken as 1.5 Ohmm); ρ_{cal}^{max} - is the maximum true specific resistance in the field - this value is determined on the basis of the dependencies $\rho_{SER} = f(\rho_{cal})$ established for KS and PKS (=50 Ohmm taken, fig. 2a and b).

e) Determination of sandness coefficient. The following formula was used for this purpose:

$$C_s = (1 - C_c) * 100\% \quad (14)$$

i) Determination of the true thickness of the layer. For this purpose, the following scheme characterizing

the angle of inclination of the layers on the blocks was developed using a structural map (fig. 5). The traditional formula used, taking into account the angle of inclination of both the layer and the well, is as follows:

$$h_h = h_f \cos(\alpha - \beta) \cos \varphi \quad (15)$$

Here, α - angle of inclination of the layer; β - inclination angle of the well; φ - azimuth of the well axis. However, since not all wells have inclinometer data, an abbreviated formula has been determined the true layer thickness using the above scheme:

$$h_{cal} = h_a \cos \eta \quad (16)$$

Here, h_a - is the assumed thickness of the layer taken from the diagram; η - is the angle taken according to the scheme, and in our case it is assumed to be 20° (fig. 5). In the Pirallahi field 377 wells are vertical and 170 are inclined.

Figure 5. Scheme characterizing the angle of inclination of layers on blocks

f) Determination of the thickness of the oil-bearing layer. The following formula was used to determine this thickness:

$$h_{o.g} = h_r C_s \quad (17)$$

Here, h_r - the real thickness of the investigation layer; C_s - is the coefficient of sandness. Based on the obtained data, a model of the research horizon for different quantities is builded. At the same time, tables on wells, horizons, tectonic blocks and final results on the object are compiled on the basis of information obtained from the research object method of the oil and gas field.

4. Results

Layers with an oil and gas saturation coefficient greater than 0.52 were selected by formation groups and the average values of all quantities were determined. The above sequence was implemented for all suite from top to bottom on tectonic blocks (table 1).

Sufficient oil and gas-bearing layer have been identified in PKCS, PKSS, KS and PKS on tectonic blocks in well cross-sections. No such layer were recorded in the Balakhany, Surakhany and Sabunchi suite.

Oil and gas-bearing layer are present in tectonic blocks I (we have II), IIa (we have IV) of the "Pereriva" formation. The total thickness of these layers was 8 m in tectonic block I (II), 5 m in II (III) and 2 m in IIa (IV). The initial balance reserves of 3883.000 tons of oil have been determined in the "Pereriva" formation on the field. The "Pereriva" formation has not been developed in the field so far. Based on the results obtained, it is proposed to conduct sampling in this layer.

PKCS is observed in all tectonic blocks. The inirical balance reserves of oil in this formation are estimated at 4296 thousand tons. The PKCS formation has not been developed in the field so far. Based on the results obtained, it is proposed to conduct sampling in this layer.

PKSS is observed in all tectonic blocks. The inirical balance reserves of oil in this formation are estimated at 6019 thousand tons.

KS is observed in all tectonic blocks. The inirical balance reserves of oil in this formation are estimated at 57.196 thousand tons.

PKS is observed in all tectonic blocks. The inirical balance reserves of oil in this formation are estimated at 30.046 thousand tons.

PKSS, KS and PKS are the objects of development in the field. Therefore, according to 443 wells surveyed at the Pirallahi oil field, the initial balance reserves of oil for these suite were estimated at 93.261 thousand tons.

As a result of processing the logging diagrams, the following additional information was obtained.

Preliminary balance oil reserves for previuly undeveloped tectonic blocks are distributed as follows: II (I) in "Pereriva"+PKCS+PKSS 8192 thousand tons; III (II) in "Pereriva"+PKCS+PKSS 639 thousand tons; IV (IIa) in "Pereriva"+PKCS+PKSS 231 thousand tons; V (IIb) in PKCS+PKSS 2138 thousand tons; VII (IIc) in PKCS+PKSS 1270 thousand tons; VIII (IVa) in PKCS+PKSS 1728 thousand tons; Total is 14.198 thousand tons.

Initial balance oil reserves in tectonic block I (III), which is not developed yet: 1792 thousand tons in PKCS; 276 thousand tons in PKSS; 2573 thousand tons in KS; 1192 thousand tons in PKS. Total is 5833 thousand tons.

Due to the lack of information on wells located in tectonic block VI (IIc), in this tectonic block was not included in the calculation.

1) A total of 87.242 thousand tons was estimated for the KS+PKS of the initial oil reserves in the field; 2) I (III) tectonic block recoverable oil reserves is 2174 thousand tons; 3) The recoverable oil reserves in tectonic blocks II (I), III (II), IV (IIa), V (IIb), VII (IIc), VIII (IVa) are 1.600 thousand tons at PKCS and 2.242 thousand tons at PKSS. 4) The recoverable oil reserves in tectonic blocks II (I), II (II), IV (IIa) are 1.447 thousand tons at "Pereriva". 5) The recoverable oil reserves of the field are 32.553 thousand tons.

5. Discussion

The results of the compiled model, cross-section and correlation schemes on suite.

According to the 2D model (the model is compiled on the whole suite - fig. 6)

Pirallahi KS_5 Porosity

Figure 6. 2D model - for example

1. By coefficient of porosity: KS5 - high values in the southeast and north; KS4 - is characterized by low values in layers; KS3 - grows in the south-eastern; KS2 - slight increase in the south-east; KS1 - high values in the north and south; PKCS - high value in the layer; PKSS - slight increase in the western and south-eastern part, an increase is observed in the lower horizons of the south-eastern part of the structure.

2. Distribution of oil saturation coefficient: KS5 - high values in the center and south-east; KS4 - the highest value in the south-east and center; KS3 - high values in the south-east and center; KS2 - declining trend; KS1 - in the center and east is normal, deteriorating to the south-east; PKCS - high value in the

east and north of the structure; PKSS - saturation is practically not observed.

3. Distribution of facies: KS5 - high sandiness in the north-west and south-west; KS4 - clayness in the senter, high sand in the north and south-east; KS3 - sand-clay transition in the eastern and western parts of the center; KS2 - good sandiness is persistent in the south-western direction and in the northern part, in the other direction the sands and clays replace each other; KS1 - the layers consist mainly of clay fractions; PKCS - clays in the south-west and south-east; PKSS - small quantities of clay-sands are observed.

Porosity and facies in the 3D model (the model is compiled on the whole suite - fig. 7):

Pirallahi porosity model, from PKS to KS_5 horizon

Pirallahi facies model, from PKS to KS_5 horizon

Figure 7. Porosity and fasies in 3D model

Porosity - grows southeast of the structure from the PKSS to the KS5 horizon. Fasie - from the PKSS to the KS5 horizon the clayness of the sandy facies along the horizon increases, and then the percentage of sandiness increases.

According to the cross-section of the field (fig. 8): To west-east direction: The cross-sectional profile of the southern parts of the structure shows the absence of

oil in the PKSS. Low oil content in PKCS is in the western part. Relative oil content is in the lower parts of the KS. Good oil content is observed in the eastern parts of structure in the KS3, KS4, KS5 horizons; In the north-south direction: Good oil content is observed in the lower horizons of KS2, KS3, KS4 and KS5 with an increase to the south.

Figure 8. Geological section: QUG - Post-Kirmaky Clay Suite (PKCS); QUQ - Post-Kirmaky Sand Suite (PKSS); QD - Kirmaky Suite (KS); QD1 - Kirmaky Suite (KS1); QD2 - Kirmaky Suite (KS2); QD3 - Kirmaky Suite (KS3); QD4 - Kirmaky Suite (KS4); QD5 - Kirmaky Suite (KS5)

Distribution of petrophysical quantities in the 3D model (the model is compiled on the whole suite - fig. 9): Clayness - average value 40 %; Porosity - average value 15 %; Sandiness - about 80 %; Oil saturation -

average value 50-60 %; Fasie - sandstone predominates.

Figure 9. Distribution of petrophysical quantities - for example

Correlation result (fig. 10): All suite are involved in well section according to the correlated profile. There is no thinning-out and the thickness of

the layers does not change so sharply (approximate average value is 15-17 m).

Figure 10. Correlation scheme: K_{mes} - porosity coefficient; C_q - percentage of sand FXM - assumed specific electric resistance; QP - spontaneous potential (SP); Bal_LD - Balakhany Suite (BS); orta sobe - middle productive series; QUG - Post-Kirmaky Clay Suite (PKCS); QUQ - Post-Kirmaky Sand Suite (PKSS); QD - Kirmaky Suite (KS); $QD1$ - Kirmaky Suite (KS1); $QD2$ - Kirmaky Suite (KS2); $QD3$ - Kirmaky Suite (KS3); $QD4$ - Kirmaky Suite (KS4); $QD5$ - Kirmaky Suite (KS5); QA - Pre-Kirmaky Suite (PKS)

6. Conclusions

1. The sandness coefficient of the collector layers of the Pirallahi field is about 80 %. This is also important in the operation of the layers.
2. As a result of the research, some oil-bearing layer with high oil content have been released.
3. Distribution graphs show that, good collectors are located in the south-eastern direction of the field.
4. In the south-eastern parts, an increase in porosity is observed in the lower horizons of the structure.
5. Clays predominate in the south-western and south-eastern parts of the structure.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Vagif Mirgamze Seyidov: Conceptualisation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft.
 Khalid Faig Melikov: Conceptualisation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft.

Acknowledgement

Sincere appreciation goes to God for life and inspiration. Thanks to ASOIU for the software and data provided during the evaluation.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Ahmedov NN, Bagirzade FA, Salayev SM (1973) Geology of oil and gas regions of Azerbaijan. Baku, 262 p.
2. Kerimov KM, Huseynov AN, Nagiyev FM et al. (2002) Geological bases of assessment of hydrocarbon resources of the Azerbaijan Republic // Geophysics news in Azerbaijan. Baku, #3-4, p. 6-8.
3. Mammadov NV, Seyidov VM, Pashayev NV (1996) About determination of productive layers in piped wells by INNЛ // Azerbaijan Oil Industry. Baku, #11, p. 11-14.
4. Pashayev NV, Seyidov VM, Sadyarov AD (2010) Estimation of field reserve parameters based on GIW data with mathematical statistical approach / Theses of the scientific conference dedicated to the 100th anniversary of Sh.Mehdiyev. BSU, Baku, p. 185-187.
5. Pashayev NV, Seyidov VM, Malikov KhF (2011) Assess the feasibility of methods for determining the permeability of rocks // Azerbaijan Oil Industry. Baku, #05, p. 3-7.
6. Seyidov VM (2009) Problems studied by geophysical control methods in field development and application of new methods // Proceedings of Azerbaijan High Technical Educational Institutions. Baku, #3(61), p. 14-17.
7. Basin YN, Qrunis EB (2004) Geophysical surveys of wells at the stage of operation of an oil and gas field // Karotajnik. Tver, #25, p. 11-15.
8. Hasanov AB, Melikov KhF, Seyidov VM (2008) Estimation of the distribution of collectors in space according to the complex of geophysical and petrophysical data // Karotajnik. Tver, #7(172), p. 50-57.
9. Konoplev YV, Kuznichov GS, Leontyev EI et al. (1986) Geophysical methods for monitoring the development of oil fields. Moscow, 221 p.
10. Vendelshteyn BY, Zoloyeva GM, Chareva NV et al. (1985) Geophysical methods for studying estimated parameters in determining oil and gas reserves. Moscow, 311 p.
11. Seyidov VM (2004) Improving control over the exploitation of deposits in Azerbaijan with the help of geophysical research methods // Azerbaijan Oil Industry. Moscow, #11, p. 108-110.
12. Seyidov VM (2005) To the question of studying some parameters during the exploitation of layers // Azerbaijan Oil Industry. Moscow, #11, p. 58-60.
13. Gutiérrez-Torres, Ludy-Amparoa, Molina-Gomez, et al. (2019) Methodology to define hydrocarbon potential in a shale reservoir based on geochemical data and well logs. *Ciencia, Tecnologia y Futuro Vol 9, Num 1: 5-14.* <https://doi.org/10.29047/01225383.147>
14. Crain. (2015). *Petrophysical Handbook*. [Online] E.R (Ross) Crain. Shareware Petrophysics Training and Reference Manual. [Cited March 10, 2015]. Available at: URL <http://spec2000.net/01-index.htm>
15. Crain, E.R Ross. (2014) *HOLGATE D. Step Program To Reduce Uncertainty In Kerogen-Rich Reservoirs: Part 1- Getting the right porosity*. Reservoir Issue 03.
16. Passey QR; et al. (2010). *From Oil-Prone Source Rock to Gas-Producing Shale Reservoir-Geologic and Petrophysical Characterization of Unconventional Shale-Gas Reservoir*. Available at: Society of Petroleum Engineers, SPE 131350/SPE International, Copyright. 29p.
17. US. EIA. (2013). *Technically Recoverable Shale Oil and Shale Gas Resources: An Assessment of 137 Shale Formations in Countries outside the United States*. Available at: <https://www.eia.gov/analysis/studies/worldshalegas/pdf/overview.pdf>
18. Craddock PR, Mosse L, Bernhardt C, Ortiz AC, Tomassini FG, Pirie IC, Saldungaray P, Pomerantz AE (2018) Matrix-adjusted shale porosity measured in horizontal wells. *Petrophysics* 59(03):288-307. <https://doi.org/10.30632/PJV59N3-2018a1>
19. Hill DG (2017) Formation evaluation. In: Hsu CS, Robinson PR (eds) *Springer handbook of petroleum technology*. Springer, Cham, pp 433-500. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-49347-3_13
20. Tiab D, Donaldson EC (2016) *Petrophysics: theory and practice of measuring reservoir rock and fluid transport properties*, 4th edn. Gulf Professional Publishing, Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2014-0-03707-0>
21. Oras Joseph Mkinga, Erik Skogen, Jon Kleppe (2020) Petrophysical interpretation in shaly sand formation of a gas field in Tanzania. *Journal of Petroleum Exploration and Production Technology*. 10:1201-1213 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13202-019-00819-x>
22. Sihui Liu, Buzhou Huang, Baozhi Pan, et al. (2015) Research on the calculation method of shale and tuff content: taking tuffaceous reservoirs of X depression in the Hailar-Tamtsag Basin as an example. *J. Geophys. Eng.* 12. 810-819. <https://academic.oup.com/jge/article/12/5/810/5106779>
23. Yunsheng W, Ailin J, Yanmei X, Jianlong F (2021) Progress on the different methods of reserves calculation in the whole life cycle of gas reservoir development. *Journal of Natural Gas Geoscience*, Volume 6, Issue 1, February, Pages 55-63.
24. Chen YQ, Tang W (2016) Annual evaluation methods for remaining recoverable reserves, remaining recoverable reserves-production ratio and remaining recoverable degree of oil and gas fields. *Acta Pet. Sin.*, 37 (6), pp. 796-801.
25. Аль-Кебси, ААМА (2019) Improving the methodology for calculating oil reserves of the Bazhenov formation by taking into account the system of fractures. p. 119-122.
26. Eremina NV (2017) Calculation of reserves and assessment of oil and gas resources. Training manual (laboratory workshop). Stavropol, 181 p.
27. Makuxo OO, Xomik VM (2019) Improving the accuracy of estimating hydrocarbon reserves for

prospecting and exploration wells according to the prms Prooil classification. Professionally about oil. № 4(14). p. 26-31.

28. Dmitry Z (2019) Improving the Accuracy of Hydrocarbon Reserves Estimation Based on an Integrated Approach November DOI:10.30987/graphicon-2019-2-164-167.

Gutiérrez-Torres, Ludy-Amparo*; Molina-Gomez, Luz-Diana; Ribón-Barrios, Helena-Margarita a;

Aristóbulo-Bejaranob; Juliao-Lemus, Tatiana-Milena c.

Gutiérrez-Torres, Ludy-Amparo*; Molina-Gomez, Luz-Diana; Ribón-Barrios, Helena-Margarita a;

Aristóbulo-Bejaranob; Juliao-Lemus, Tatiana-Milena c.